

Optimization of Levofloxacin Removal by Corn Husk and its Activated Carbon

Muhammad Afzaal^{1*}, Syeda Saira Iqbal^{1,2*}, Rohama Nassir¹, Neha Javid John¹ and Aysha Arif¹

1. Sustainable Development Study Center, Government College, University Lahore
2. University of Management and Technology, Lahore

*Corresponding author e-mail: dr.afzaal@gcu.edu.pk saira.iqbal186@gmail.com

SUMMARY

Pharmaceutical productions use a huge amount of dissolved chemicals, which can trigger negative consequences. Pharmaceutical wastewater includes a high concentration of antibiotics, which can be handled in a variety of ways, including chemical and physical methods. In this study, corn husk was used for the synthesis of an effective adsorbent. In batch experimentation, simply crushed corn husk samples and activated carbon solution have been distinctively analyzed by treating them at different temperatures (150°C, 200°C, 250°C, 300°C, 350°C, and 400°C). The impact on varied temperatures revealed that temperature rise produced an increase in adsorption from 150°C to 400°C, although it is an exothermic process. Varied PH (2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14) absorbance capacity increases when the solution is more acidic. The adsorbent is dependent on the contact time allowed (35, 50, 70, 90, 120, 140, 180 minutes), which increases the adsorption percentage. Amount dosage (0.6 g, 1 g, 1.5 g, 1.7 g, 2 g) to check the adsorption capacity and efficiency at four different sieves The adsorbent's size parameters (200 mm, 50 mm, 30 mm, 10 mm) dose increases of corn husk adsorbent resulted in no substantial improvement; it did slightly enhance adsorption%. Given the SEM images, the nanocrystalline surface of the bioadsorbent contains pores and is also layered. These features showed that corn husk acts as a biosorbent; white nanoparticles indicate antibiotics have adsorbed on the structure of the biosorbent. The FTIR spectrum levofloxacin adsorption, interaction among cornhusks, and levofloxacin by adsorption process

Keywords: Corn-Husk; Adsorbent; Wastewater; Levofloxacin, Antibiotic, Pharmaceuticals.

Citation: Afzaal, M., S. S. Iqbal, R. Nassir, N. J. John, and A. Arif. 2023. Optimization of Levofloxacin Removal by Corn Husk and its Activated Carbon. *International Journal of Forest Sciences* 3(3):170-193.

Received: July, 2023; **Accepted:** September, 2023

INTRODUCTION

Wastewater discharged by pharmaceuticals and medicines contains a large number of chemicals and solvents used in their manufacture and manufacturing processes. Almost all pharmaceutical effluent contains 99.99 percent water, which is hazardous in many ways, and it also contains materials that are present in the form of dissolved solids. It may also be detrimental to human health as well as to nature and life on Earth (Ahmed *et al.*, 2015). It is important to treat this sort of contaminated water.

Pharmaceutical wastewater contains a large number of antibiotics that may be treated in a variety of ways, including chemical and physical procedures. The presence of antibiotics in bodies of water is becoming a major hazard to civilization and public health. Antibiotics are removed from wastewater using biomass and agricultural waste (Enderset et al, 2012). Corn husk has also been utilized in the production of biochar. Corn husk may be used as an absorbent because it can absorb antibiotics from pharmaceutical wastewater (Chen *et al.*, 2019). Pharmaceutical industries produce medicines such as penicillin, antibiotics, and others that are often highly solid, have low PH and high BOD levels, and should not be managed with residential wastewater. Water is contaminated by a variety of noxious compounds, and while each chemical may be handled precisely, it cannot be addressed broadly. Specific wastewater treatment is being carried out. Treatment of environmental wastewater is critical from the standpoint of public health and the ecosystem (Li *et al.*, 2017). Antibiotic-contaminated water is becoming a worldwide environmental problem. Because of the rise in population and disease rate, the consumption rate of antibiotics, as well as their exposure to the environment, is essential to minimize. Existing wastewater treatment technology is incapable of properly removing antibiotics from sewage; innovative and low-cost technology is essential.

Techniques such as Biosorption and bioaccumulation are environmentally acceptable alternatives (Ramachandra *et al.*, 2006). These non-traditional approaches have benefits over traditional ways. Because of the existence of metal-binding functional groups, a wide range of natural materials such as microbial biomass, Agriculture-manure, and industrial derivatives were proposed as possible bio-sorbents for heavy metal removal, due to the presence of metal-binding functional groups, heavy metal removal is possible (Ahmad *et al.*, 2014) Temperature, starting concentration of the metal ion, PH, bio-sorbent dosage, and agitation speed are all process factors that influenced biosorption. In addition, before usage, the biomass can also be modified chemically as well as physically.

Levofloxacin is an antibiotic that is being utilized to treat a variety of bacterial illnesses. LEV is a quinolone antibiotic, which is a kind of antibiotic. It reacts by preventing bacterial expansion. LEV is exclusively addressing bacterial sicknesses. It is ineffective against viral infections such as colds and the common flu. In 1996, Levofloxacin was first authorized for medicinal usage in the US. It is on the WHO's List of Vital Medicines. It is accessible as a common drug. In 2018, LEV was the 160th greatest often prescribed medicine in the US, with over 3 million prescriptions written. Levofloxacin comes in pill, injectable, and oral solution forms. Levofloxacin is used to treat diseases such as RTI i.e., Respiratory Tract Infections), UTI i.e., Urinary Tract Infections, meningitis, prostatitis, pelvic inflammatory illness, anthrax traveler's diarrhea, TB, cellulitis, endocarditis. It is accessible orally, intravenously, and as an optical drop (Freitas *et al.*, 2018). The major source of antibiotics (Levofloxacin) in the environment is the discharge of partly digested antibiotics by human beings and animals. The objectives of this research are to remediate water that has been contaminated by the dumping of pharmaceuticals. To devise a low-cost biosorption method that makes use of readily accessible biomass, to ensure the protection of the environment through effective waste management measures and provide awareness to illiterate people not to use this infected water without any such

treatment and examine the optimization of Levofloxacin antibiotic biosorption. The novelty of the study is the absorption of antibiotic (Levofloxacin) has been done by the absorbent i.e., Corn Husk. The novelty of this study is that wastewater is treated at several parameters (four different mean sizes), and varied condition has been applied (temperature fluctuation, PH, Contact Time, and Amount dosage). This research work is novel in terms use of an expensive and easily available source of Corn husk biomass for the optimization of Levofloxacin can be productive soon for covering the scientific gaps in earlier studies of Pakistan, also the agricultural waste will be utilized for an upright purpose and wastewater can be treated efficiently with less environmental and health impact.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SAMPLE COLLECTION

Corn has been acquired from the local village of Punjab, Pakistan. The maize was peeled off and the remaining cob was placed in the laboratory for further experimentation. Levofloxacin (LEV) 250mg tablet has been purchased from the local pharmacy of Lahore. Distilled water is collected from the laboratory. Pharmaceutical wastewater is generated in the laboratory.

STUDY AREA

Getz Pharma (PVT) Limited is Pakistan's largest branded common pharmaceutical business and is functioning internationally. It complies with local and international regulatory requirements and manufactures world-class branded generic pharmaceutical goods.

CORN COB/ HUSK

The cob of the corn is the middle core part of the corn. Cob is the region where the maize/ kernels grow. The ear of the corn is shucked and removed from the plant around the ear. The part of the most removed and discarded corn is called the Cob/ Husk of corn. The inside of the cob is white and has a consistency alike the foam made of plastic. Despite its low nutritional value, the cob of corn can be used as fiber in ruminant livestock feeds. Cobs absorb moisture and offer a responsive surface for animal bedding. Typically, the maize cob is seen as agricultural waste. This organic and natural waste material has the potential to be utilized in the industry in general, and in construction buildings in particular (Pinto *et al.*, 2012)

ACTIVATED CARBONS

Activated Carbons are extremely microporous carbons with a high internal surface area and absorbency, and they are the most often utilized adsorbents in industry organic compound removal from water streams. As a raw material for the manufacture of activated carbon, any inexpensive material with low inorganic and high carbon content can be utilized (Bansal *et al.*, 2005)

SAMPLE PREPARATION/ ABSORBENT PREPARATION

The cob corn's whole corn is considered a vegetable. Several grains, including corn, are classified as fruits to make matters even more complicated. This is because they

are derived from the plant's seed or the flower part. Corn is therefore a vegetable, a whole grain, and a fruit. Corn (*Zea Mayes*) is available and commonly accessible in Pakistan throughout the year. I have collected 2 kg of corn cob with peeled maize from a village in Punjab, Pakistan. Then washed with double distilled water and remove the dirt and other soluble pollutants from the cob. The washed corn cobs have been dried firstly under the sunlight for a whole week (7 days). Then I put the dried corn cobs in the Oven Memmert UM 200 for drying the remaining moisture. The oven temperature was set at 49° C for 6 hours. After removing the moisture, the cobs become crusty and easy to crush. The fully dried cobs are then crushed in the laboratory with the help of a Simple laboratory Crusher, the remaining hard crumbs were also ground in the grinder to make precise stuff from the Corn Cobs. After crushing and grinding the cobs precisely, the crushed material was then sieved to make different size parameters for our analysis. The crushed material is sieved in 4 parameters:

- i. Mean Size of 50 Micrometer = 297 micron = 0.297 inches
- ii. Mean Size of 30 Micrometer = 595 micron = 0.595 inches
- iii. Mean Size of 200Micrometer = 74 micron = 0.074 inches
- iv. Mean Size of 10 Micrometer = 2000 micron = 2 inches

After distinguishing the crushed powder in 4 different parameters, 4 types of absorbents were ready for our experimentation and further treatments.

DRYING SIEVED SAMPLES IN MEMMERT OVEN UM 200

The sieved samples of 10mm, 30mm, 200mm, and 50mm were again dried in the Oven at 800° C for approximately two hours. Then they were labeled and placed from crucibles into zip-lock plastic bags. The sieved samples of 50mm, 30mm, 200mm, and 10mm were placed in a desiccator for 3 hours to cool down before further experimentation.

Batch Experiment

Experimentation was carried out by adding the absorbent and absorbate into the sample that carries the specific concentration of contaminants with the ratio of biomass/ solid (Tan *et al.*, 2020)

Adsorption Experimentation

Among the several water treatment strategies available, the adsorption process by biomass or adsorbents has the potential to be one of the most effective ways for the treatment and removal of contaminants in wastewater (Baig, 2020)

Performance

Adsorption Experimentation:

- i. Took 1000 ml of distilled water in a beaker and took 250 mg of Levofloxacin (LEV) tablet and crushed it in a Mortar& Pestle and made a fine powder of it.
- ii. Placed the powdered antibiotic material on an analytical weighing balance.
 - a. Weight of Powdered LEV Tablet= 0.3474 g

- iii. The 0.3474 g of LEV was then dissolved in 1000ml of distilled water and made a synthesized antibiotic solution, and separate the dissolved sample into 4 small beakers, each beaker was filled with 100ml of antibiotic solution.
- iv. 2 grams of 100mm sieved sample was measured on the analytical weighing balance. Same for the mean size of 30mm, 10mm, 50mm, and 200mm sieved samples. Dissolved the 2 grams of absorbent in 100ml antibiotics solutions. For dissolving the absorbent into the absorbate, the beakers were placed on the magnetic stirrer. The magnetic stirrer was set at 180 rpm (revolution per minute) at 29° C, and the timer set for each beaker was of 1 hour and 20 minutes.
- v. After dilution, the solution was cooled at room temperature, and filtrated with Whatman filter paper. The liquid we got was then sealed in the bottles and the filtrate material was placed in the oven so that the moisture content may get dried for further experimentation.

Absorbent preparation for Activated Carbon

- i. The remaining solution of 1000 ml in a beaker was used for the activated carbon analysis.
- ii. The 0.3474 g of LEV was then dissolved in 1000ml of distilled water and made a synthesized antibiotic solution, and separate the dissolved sample into 2 small beakers, each beaker was filled with 100ml of antibiotic solution.
- iii. Now place the 2 grams of 100mm sieve sample and 30mm sieve sample in a China dish and place the sample in the muffle furnace at 650° C for 40 minutes. The sample of crushed corn was burnt and turned into ash.
- iv. Now the ash has been weighed on the analytical weighing balance
 - a. For the mean size of 100mm, the Sieve Ash sample weight was = 3.1692g
 - b. For the mean size of 30mm Sieve Ash sample weight was = 2.6054g
- v. The 3.1692 g of 100mm of sieve ash sample was added to 100 ml of antibiotic solution. So as 2.6054g of 30mm of sieve ash sample was added in 100ml of antibiotic solution.
- vi. In the 100mm solution 3 drops of Hydrochloric acid in it a place the solution on the magnetic stirrer at 290 rpm (revolution per minute) at 150° C, and the timer was set for each beaker was of 40 minutes.
- vii. The 30mm solution was diluted without HCL magnetic stirrer at 290 rpm (revolution per minute) at 150° C, and the timer set for each beaker was 40 minutes.
- viii. After dilution, the solution was cooled at room temperature, and filtrated with Whatman filter paper. The liquid we got was then sealed in the bottles and the filtrate material was placed in the oven so that the moisture content may get dried for further analysis.

Batch studies/ Analysis Performed in Laboratory

PH Analysis: PH analysis has been done in 50mm, 30mm, 200mm, and 10mm antibiotic solutions has been done in both simple and activated carbon samples. 6 bottles were taken (which 4 are of the sieve size of 10mm, 30mm, 200mm, and 10mm solutions) and (2 are of activated carbon) and a solution in a beaker in which 0.5 g of Hydrochloric acid (HCL) was added in each beaker. The PH meter (PH/ ORP/ Temperature Meter PH 210) has been used in the experimentation. The prob has been

dipped thoroughly in each beaker and the acidic fluctuations have been observed. After observing the acidic fluctuations, 0.5g of Sodium hydroxide was added to the beakers dropwise.

Bio adsorbent Dosage Effect

In the previous analysis, 2 grams of absorbent was taken i.e., crushed corn husk to make an antibiotic solution. In a 500ml flask, 50ml of the antibiotic solution has been added to the flasks, and different doses of absorbent: 2.5 g, 3 g, 3.5 g, and 4 g were added in each flask. Each flask was agitated on Diahann Digital Hotplate Stirrer MSH-20D for 1 hour at 35 ° C temperature. The solutions were filtered with the Whatman filter paper and Spectro Scan MSH 20D for 1 hour at 35° C. The absorbance was determined by Whatman filter paper and Spectro Scan 80 DUV- VIS spectrophotometer. In dose analysis, the percentage of removal by alteration in dose has been assessed. After the 2-gram solution, the dosage quantity has increased by 2.5 g then 3 g, 3.5 g, and 4 grams. Absorption capacity by fluctuation in absorbent capacity has been observed.

TEMPERATURE EFFECT

The analysis of absorption was assessed at different temperatures. The antibiotic solutions of 10mm, 200mm, 30mm, and 50mm have been placed on the magnetic stirrer with varied temperature sets on the magnetic stirrer. The first Temperature range was 150° C then 4 parameters with 1 sample of Activated carbon were placed on a magnetic stirrer at 200° C, 250° C, 300° C, 350° C, and 400° C. The absorbance capacity was analyzed and the results are shown in a graphical representation.

CONTACT TIME

The contact time between the Levofloxacin and absorbate has significance importance in the experiment for the analysis of adsorption in wastewater treatment. The readings were collected with the help of Spectro Scan 80 DUV- VIS spectrophotometer within a different interval of time. The first reading was recorded at 0-35 minutes then from 35 -50 minutes, 50 -70 minutes, 70 -90 minutes, 90 -120 minutes, 120-140 minutes, and 140 – 180 minutes. The absorbance capacity has been noticed at different contact times (Balarak, et, al. 2020).

FTIR ANALYSIS

FTIR stands for Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. The vibrational was used to scan the absorption capacity of the absorbent (He&Chenet, 2021) The analytical method was applied to determine the bonding mechanism of the culture (sample). FT/IR- 600 (JASCO) has been used for the analysis (Tayloret *al.*, 2020)

SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPE (SEM)

The filtrate samples were again analyzed in the scanning electron microscope. The samples were placed in the SEM (KYKY- EM3200) for scanning and the electron beam over the surface was observed and the image has been created (De Silveira *et al.*, 2020)

RESULTS

The adsorption technique for removing antibiotic residues from water and wastewater has been critically examined based on substantial scientific studies and my analysis that were being performed. To summarize, adsorption is an efficient approach for removing antibiotics from polluted waters. The results of the absorbance capacity of antibiotic solution with varied sieve samples are as follows:

The PH effect from 0 to 14 reveals that the absorbance was greatest at PH 6. The acidic solution has a higher absorbance capacity, whereas the basic solution has a lower absorbance capacity. However, the rate of adsorption was significantly decreased at or above 7,8 PH. The trend was similar across all four adsorbent sizes, 200mm, 50mm, 30mm, and 10mm, although the amount of adsorption done by each type was different as indicated in the figures.

The profile of the absorbance of the PH of 200mm is shown in the figure 1. With the addition of Hydrochloric acid (HCl), the PH exceeds the maximum then the bar drops down gradually with the addition of Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) base. At PH 14 the bar drops at the lowest. The biomass absorbance is slightly dependent on the PH for adsorption. So, the trend for PH was inconsistency.

Figure 1: Adsorption percentage by variation in pH of adsorbent 200 mm sieve size.

PH FOR 200MM ACTIVATED CARBON SOLUTION

The profile of the absorbance of the PH of 200mm Activated Carbon Solution has shown in figure 2. With the addition of Hydrochloric acid (HCl), the PH exceeds the maximum of 8.9 at 6 PH then the bar drops down gradually with the addition of Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) base. At PH 14 the bar drops at the lowest.

Figure 2: Adsorption percentage by variation in pH of adsorbent 200 mm sieve size in activated carbon solution.

PH for 50mm

The profile of the absorbance of the PH of 50mm is shown in figure 3. With the addition of Hydrochloric acid (HCl), the PH exceeds the maximum 7.3 absorbance capacity comparatively less than 200 mm comparatively, after that the bar drops down gradually with the addition of Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) base. At PH 14 the bar drops at the lowest.

Figure 3: Adsorption percentage by variation in pH of adsorbent 50 mm sieve size.

PH Effect for 30mm

The profile of the absorbance of the PH of 30mm as shown in figure 4. With the addition of Hydrochloric acid (HCl), the PH exceeds the maximum 5.3 absorbance capacity at PH 6 comparatively less than 200 mm, 50 mm comparatively, after that the bar drops down gradually with the addition of Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) base. At PH 14 the bar drops at the lowest.

Figure 4: Adsorption percentage by variation in pH of adsorbent 30 mm sieve size.

PH Effect for 10mm

The profile of the absorbance of PH of 10mm as shown in figure 5. With the addition of Hydrochloric acid (HCl), the PH exceeds the maximum 4.9 absorbance capacity at PH 6 comparatively less than 200 mm, 50 mm, and 30mm comparatively, after that the bar drops down gradually with the addition of Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) base. At PH 14 the bar drops at the lowest.

Figure.5: Adsorption percentage by variation in pH of adsorbent 10 mm sieve size.

DOSE ABSORPTION EFFECT

The impact of adsorbent on the percentage of levofloxacin adsorption was studied by varying the adsorbent dose from 0.6g to 2g. The trend of the percentage of adsorption is uneven, implying that the amount of corn husk used as an adsorbent is dependent in part on the dose of the adsorbent supplied in the aqueous solution. The dose increases of corn husk adsorbent resulted in no substantial improvement; however, it did slightly enhance the adsorption %. The pattern was identical when all four adsorbent parameters were changed, 200mm, 50mm, 30mm, and 10mm, however, the proportion of adsorption done by each size of adsorbent was significantly different as shown in figures.

Dose Adsorption 200mm

The profile of the absorbance of the dose effect of 200mm solution has shown in the figure 6. The biomass absorbance depends on the quantity of dose added to the solution. The adsorption capacity has been fluctuating with the increase and decrease in the dose quantity. 0.6 g, 1 g, 1.5 g, 1.7 g, and 2g of adsorbent has been added to the solution, in all these quantities 0.6 g has the maximum absorbance capacity, while 2 g has the minimum absorbance capacity.

Figure: 6 Adsorption percentage by variation in amount dosage of adsorbent 200 mm sieve size.

Dose Adsorption Effect in Activated Carbon Solution 200mm

The profile of the absorbance of the dose effect of activated carbon 200mm solution has shown in figure 7. The biomass absorbance depends on the quantity of dose added to the solution. The adsorption capacity has been fluctuating with the increase and decrease in the dose quantity. 0.6 g, 1 g, 1.5 g, 1.7 g, and 2g of adsorbent has been added to the solution, in all these quantities 0.6 g has the maximum absorbance capacity, while 2 g has the minimum absorbance capacity.

Figure 7: Adsorption percentage by variation in amount dosage of adsorbent 200 mm sieve size activated carbon.

Dose Adsorption 50mm

The profile of the absorbance of the dose effect of the 50mm solution has shown in figure 8. The biomass absorbance depends on the quantity of dose added to the solution. The adsorption capacity has been fluctuating with the increase and decrease in the dose quantity. 0.6 g, 1 g, 1.5 g, 1.7 g, and 2g of adsorbent has been added to the solution, in all these quantities g has the maximum absorbance capacity, while 2 g has the minimum absorbance capacity.

Figure 8 Adsorption percentage by variation in amount dosage of adsorbent 50 mm sieve size.

Dose Adsorption 30mm

The profile of the absorbance of the dose effect of the 30mm solution has shown in figure 9. The biomass absorbance depends on the quantity of dose added to the solution. The adsorption capacity has been fluctuating with the increase and decrease in the dose quantity. 0.6 g, 1 g, 1.5 g, 1.7 g, and 2g of adsorbent has been added to the solution, in all these quantities 0.6 g has the maximum absorbance capacity, while 2 g has the minimum absorbance capacity.

Figure 9: Adsorption percentage by variation in amount dosage of adsorbent 30 mm sieve.

Dose Adsorption 10mm

The profile of the absorbance of the dose effect of the 10mm solution has shown in figure 10. The biomass absorbance depends on the quantity of dose added to the solution. The adsorption capacity has been fluctuating with the increase and decrease in the dose quantity. 0.6 g in which 31 % was the maximum absorbance, 1 g, 1.5 g, 1.7 g, and 2g of adsorbent has been added in the solution, in all these quantities 0.6g has the maximum absorbance capacity, while 2 g has the minimum absorbance capacity.

Figure 10: Adsorption percentage by variation in amount dosage of adsorbent 200 mm sieve size.

TEMPERATURE EFFECT

The effect of temperature variation from 150° C to 400° C in which revealed that temperature rise produced an increase in adsorption from 150° C to 400° C. However, at or above 400° C, the rate of adsorption was considerably reduced. The rise in temperature and fall in adsorption capacity suggested that the adsorption process was exothermic. Except at maximum temperature, the trend was constant through the change in the temperature of the levofloxacin synthetic solution with adsorbent. This suggests that the use of corn husk as an adsorbent with synthetic levofloxacin solution is temperature dependent. The trend was comparable across all four adsorbent sizes, 200mm, 50mm, 30mm, and 10mm, but the proportion of adsorption done by each size was significantly different, as indicated in the figures.

Temperature Effect on 200mm

The profile of the absorbance by Temperature of 200mm solution has shown in figure 11. The biomass absorbance depends on the varied temperature solution. The adsorption capacity has been fluctuating with the increase and decrease of the temperature. 300° C in which 60 % absorbance was the maximum absorbance, while 150° C has the minimum absorbance capacity.

Temperature Effect on 200mm Activated Carbon Solution

The profile of the absorbance by Temperature of 10mm solution has shown in figure 12. The biomass absorbance depends on the varied temperature solution. The

adsorption capacity has been fluctuating with the increase and decrease of the temperature. 300° C in which 60 % absorbance was the maximum absorbance, while 150° C has the minimum absorbance capacity.

Figure 11: Adsorption percentage by variation in temperature with adsorbent 200 mm sieve size.

Figure 12: Adsorption percentage by variation in amount dosage of adsorbent 200 mm sieve size activated.

Temperature Effect on 50mm

The profile of the absorbance by Temperature of 50 mm solution has shown in figure 13. The biomass absorbance depends on the varied temperature solution. The adsorption capacity has been fluctuating with the increase and decrease of the temperature. 300° C in which 51 % absorbance was the maximum absorbance, while 150° C has the minimum absorbance capacity.

Figure 13: Adsorption percentage by variation in amount dosage of adsorbent 50 mm sieve size.

Temperature Effect on 30mm

The profile of the absorbance by Temperature of 30 mm solution has shown in figure 14. The biomass absorbance depends on the varied temperature solution. The adsorption capacity has been fluctuating with the increase and decrease of the temperature. 300° C in which 48.1 % absorbance was the maximum absorbance, while 150° C has the minimum absorbance capacity.

Figure 14 Adsorption percentage by variation in amount dosage of adsorbent 30 mm sieve size.

Temperature Effect on 10mm

The profile of the absorbance by Temperature of 10 mm solution has shown in figure 15. The biomass absorbance depends on the varied temperature solution. The adsorption capacity has been fluctuating with the increase and decrease of the

temperature. 300° C in which 40 % absorbance was the maximum absorbance, while 150° C has the minimum absorbance capacity.

Figure 15: Adsorption percentage by variation in amount dosage of adsorbent 10 mm sieve size.

EFFECT ON CONTACT TIME

The effect of adsorbent on the percentage of levofloxacin adsorption was investigated by altering contact duration from 50, 70, 90, 120, 140, and 180 minutes. The % adsorption trend is uneven, indicating that the amount of corn husk employed as an adsorbent is also dependent on the contact time allowed in the aqueous solution. The contact duration of corn husk adsorbent did not result in a significant improvement; nevertheless, it did marginally increase the adsorption percent. When all four adsorbent parameters were altered, 200mm, 50mm, 30mm, and 10mm, the pattern remained the same; nevertheless, the proportion of adsorption done by each size of adsorbent was considerably different, as shown in the figure.

Effect on Contact Time 200mm

The profile of the absorbance by the contact time of the 200 mm solution has shown in figure 16. The biomass absorbance depends on the contact time. The adsorption capacity has been fluctuating with the increase and decrease in the contact time. The contact time of 90 minutes has the maximum absorbance, while 180 minutes has the minimum absorbance capacity.

Effect on 200mm Contact Time Activated Carbon Solution

The profile of the absorbance by the contact time of the 200 mm solution has shown in figure 17. The biomass absorbance depends on the contact time. The adsorption capacity has been fluctuating with the increase and decrease in the contact time. The contact time of 70 minutes has the maximum absorbance, while 180 minutes has the minimum absorbance capacity.

Effect on Contact Time 50mm

The absorbance profile by the contact time of the 50 mm solution is shown in figure 18. The biomass absorbance depends on the contact time. The adsorption capacity has been fluctuating with the increase and decrease in the contact time. The contact time

of 50 minutes has the maximum absorbance, while 180 minutes has the minimum absorbance capacity.

Figure 16 Adsorption percentage by variation in contact time by adsorbent 200 mm sieve size.

Figure 17: Adsorption percentage by variation in contact time by adsorbent 200 mm sieve size activated carbon solution.

Figure18: Adsorption percentage by variation in contact time by adsorbent 50 mm sieve size.

Effect on Contact Time 30mm

The profile of the absorbance by the contact time of the 30 mm solution has shown in figure 19. The biomass absorbance depends on the contact time. The adsorption capacity has been fluctuating with the increase and decrease in the contact time. The contact time of 70 minutes has the maximum absorbance, while 180 minutes has the minimum absorbance capacity.

Figure 19: Adsorption percentage by variation in contact time by adsorbent 30 mm sieve size.

Effect on Contact Time 10mm

The profile of the absorbance by the contact time of the 10 mm solution has shown in figure 20. The biomass absorbance depends on the contact time. The adsorption capacity has been fluctuating with the increase and decrease in the contact time. The contact time of 35 minutes has the maximum absorbance, while 180 minutes has the minimum absorbance capacity.

Figure 20: Adsorption percentage by variation in contact time by adsorbent 10 mm.

SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPE RESULTS

Given the SEM images, the nanocrystalline surface of bio adsorbent contains pores and is also layered and the feature results showed that these features can act as bio-sorbent on the given bio adsorbent showed the small white color Nano particles indicated that antibiotics have been adsorbed on the structure of bio-sorbent and have taken the place of pores.

FOURIER TRANSFORMED INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY

The FTIR analysis aims to determine the functional group of a sample. Corn husks contain fiber (cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin), proteins, and carbohydrates. Bond with the chemical formula of $(C_6H_{10}O_5)_n$ where n refers to the degree of polymerization. Structurally, hemicellulose is similar to cellulose which is a polymer of sugar that makes them different in that cellulose is made up of glucose while hemicellulose is composed of a variety of sugars. Lignin is a three-dimensional polymer composed of phenyl propane units established through ether bonds (C-O-C) and carbon bonds (C-C). Amide bonds consist of C = O. The peaks at 3278.35 and 3412.78 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the N-H and -COOH stretching vibrations. Also, 1730 cm^{-1} are characteristic of (C=O) of aromatic rings, respectively. The FTIR spectrum Showed levofloxacin adsorption and interaction between the corn husk and levofloxacin as a result of the adsorption process.

DISCUSSION

With the discovery of penicillin in 1928 by Alexander Fleming, the usage of pharmaceuticals has become the gold standard for handling bacterial infections of all types. Nowadays antibiotics are utilized in numerous human activities across the globe, including fish farming, aquaculture, agronomy, and livestock husbandry, in addition to healthcare and veterinary treatment (Yoshizawa, 2020). In this study, we are focusing on the Levofloxacin antibiotic. As a result, wastewater from agriculture, hospices, farms, or municipal sewage treatment services is increasingly probable to include antibiotics, which ultimately reach environmental niches without any proceeding history of interaction among these compounds through fertilization in soil and seepage of water. Many antibiotics are resistant to degradation due to their complex chemical structures, and they can persist in the environment, mainly in polluted regions, where they are considered to apply a positive assortment pressure on antibiotic-resistant bacteria (Rasschaert, 2020). Pharmaceuticals are a prominent category of micropollutants that are causing increasing concern. These pharmaceuticals are chemotherapeutic chemicals that are used in animal farming and anthropological health to avoid or treat infections, as progress agents, and seldom as food preservers. Pharmaceuticals have entered all sections of the ecosystem through wastewater discharges and agricultural runoff due to partial or incomplete metabolism and ineffective removal during wastewater treatment.

The detrimental impact of antibiotic product manufacture on the natural environment is widely documented. Though, it is commonly uncontrolled, which means that the very harmful impact on both the human body and animals continues without a conclusion and a proper end has been seen. In recent years, worldwide

associations and the drug business have started to see the hindering effect pharma items have on the climate on a worldwide scale (Patel *et al.*, 2020)

Antibiotics infiltrate the environment at different stages of their life cycle, notably during the production process in industries. One of the utmost serious risks is that releasing antibiotics into the surroundings endorses the natural expansion of antibiotic-resistant bacteria that are more difficult to cure.

Although it is a worldwide issue, as with other ecological issues antibiotic pollution, likewise, other environmental challenges, has a more immediate and significant impact on the persons who live near manufacturing sites and whose water and food supplies are polluted with antibiotics (Kraemer *et al.*, 2019) The contamination of pharma items into the environment moreover antagonistically influences creatures, especially fish living in antibiotic wastewater. Waterbodies and aquatic environments can contaminate directly by pharmaceutical companies and plants or by other sources of humans and animals (Brodin *et al.*, 2014) As these compounds find their way into terrestrial and aquatic environments, they can have an impact on the health and behavior of wildlife, including insects, aquatic bodies, birds, and other creatures.

Many treatment methods are presently in use for the treatment of antibiotic wastewater. Anthropogenic activities may alter and contaminate the usual condition of water, which in turn cause significant environmental damage to waterways and oceans and prevent its use for activities such as agriculture (Sonune *et al.*, 2004). Due to such problems, it is important to treat polluted water using suitable water treatment procedures so that the treated wastewater may be used and become a part of the environment again. Efficient ways for removing extremely hazardous chemicals from water have piqued the public's interest. For the removal of antibiotics from contaminated water and wastewater, a variety of approaches such as remediation procedures, conventional processes, photolysis, Membrane method/ technique Nano-filtration process, ultra-filtration, reverse osmosis, and chlorination processes have been utilized. Because they frequently require significant capital and operational expenses, these approaches have been proven to be restricted. Various process factors such as pH, temperature, contact time, and bio-sorbent dosage, all affect biosorption (Wang *et al.*, 2020)

In addition, before usage, the biomass can be changed physically and chemically. The procedure may be made more cost-effective by regenerating and recycling the bio-sorbent once the antibiotics have been removed or absorbed (Rashed *et al.*, 2013) Biological removal involves the utilization of microorganisms, plant-derived materials, agricultural or industrial wastes, biopolymers, and other similar substances. In this study, we have used the Corn Husk (biomass) as an absorbent.

Biosorption processes are simple operation technique, no extra nutrients are required, also it has a low operative cost with high efficiency, also there is no such requirement of the (COD) chemical oxygen demand which is the chief requirement of the other conventional wastewater treatment methods (Torres *et al.*, 2020) Biosorption can remove pollutants even at low concentrations and is especially useful for antibiotic removal due to toxicity. Biosorption also has no such risk of harmful consequences, moreover, this technique is an eco-friendly technique (Abdi *et*

al.,2015)So, keeping in view all of these benefits, the bio-sorption technique seems to be accurate for our study, so in this study, we opted for the biosorption technique for our analysis. Various studies have proven that the corn husk/ cob are an efficient absorbent that can absorb suspended particles, heavy metals, and pharmaceuticals to a good extent. Corn is therefore a vegetable, a whole grain, and a fruit. (Pinto *et al.*,2012). Corn (*Zea Mayes*) is available commonly in Pakistan throughout the year. I have collected 2 kg of corn cob with peeled maize from a village in Punjab, Pakistan. The corn cobs are washed with double distilled water so that the dirt and other soluble pollutants from the cob may get removed. The washed corn cobs have been dried and then crushed; the crushed particles are then sieved into 4 parameters.

- i. Mean Size of 50 Micrometer i.e., 297 microns = 0.297 inches
- ii. Mean Size of 30 Micrometer i.e., 595 microns = 0.595 inches
- iii. Mean Size of 200Micrometer i.e., 74 micron = 0.074 inches
- iv. Mean Size of 10 Micrometer i.e., 2000 microns = 2 inches

Two types of experimentation have been done. The Batch Experiment in which the experimentation was carried out by adding the absorbent and absorbate into the sample that carries the specific concentration of contaminants with the ratio of biomass/ solid (Ta *et al.*, 2020) and the Adsorption Experimentation among the several water treatment strategies available, the adsorption process by biomass or adsorbents has the potential to be one of the most effective ways for the treatment and removal of contaminants in wastewater (Baig *et al.*, 2020)

Overall, the finer (powdered) the absorbent is the more efficient absorbent it does keeping in view the absorbance capacity with varied PH, The PH effect from 0 to 14 reveals that the absorbance was greatest at PH 6. The acidic solution has a higher absorbance capacity, whereas the basic solution has a lower absorbance capacity. However, the rate of adsorption was significantly decreased at or above 7,8 PH. The trend was similar across all four adsorbent sizes, 200mm, 50mm, 30mm, and 10mm, although the amount of adsorption done by each type was fluctuating. The activated carbon solution has more absorbance capacity because of the tiny and fine powdered solution. Also, for the dose adsorption effect, the impact of absorbent on the percentage of levofloxacin adsorption was studied by varying the adsorbent dose from 0.6g to 2g. The trend of the percentage of adsorption is uneven, implying that the amount of corn husk used as an adsorbent is dependent in part on the dose of the adsorbent supplied in the aqueous solution. The dose increases of corn husk absorbent resulted in no substantial improvement; however, it did slightly enhance the adsorption %. Considering the impact on temperature variation from 150° C to 400° C in which revealed that temperature rise produced an increase in adsorption from 150° C to 400° C. However, at or above 400° C, the rate of adsorption was considerably reduced. The rise in temperature and fall in adsorption capacity suggested that the adsorption process was exothermic.

Except at maximum temperature, the trend was constant through the change in the temperature of the levofloxacin synthetic solution with adsorbent. This suggests that the use of corn husk as an adsorbent with synthetic levofloxacin solution is temperature dependent. According to the varied contact time, % adsorption trend was noticed as uneven, indicating that the amount of corn husk employed as an adsorbent is also dependent on the contact time allowed in the aqueous solution. The contract

duration of corn husk absorbent did not result in a significant improvement; nevertheless, it did marginally increase the adsorption percent. The effect of absorbent on the percentage of levofloxacin adsorption was investigated by altering contact duration from 50, 70, 90, 120, 140, and 180 minutes. The activated carbon solution and the simple solution of 200mm have the highest absorbance capacity at 70 – 90 minutes.

These were the analysis of the Batch experimentation. For adsorption experimentation, the filtrates were analyzed by SEM (Scanning electron microscope) and FTIR (Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy) in which the results have been shown in a graphical form. The FTIR analysis aims to determine the functional group of a sample. The FTIR spectrum Showed levofloxacin adsorption and interaction between the corn husk and levofloxacin as a result of the adsorption process. The SEM analysis shows that the absorbent can act as an absorbent, the nanocrystalline surface of bio adsorbent shows the pores and is also layered. Nanoparticles indicated that antibiotics have been adsorbed on the structure of bio-sorbent and have taken the place of pores. In this study, the absorption of antibiotic (Levofloxacin) has been done by the bio-sorbent i.e., Corn Husk. The novelty of this study is that wastewater is treated at several parameters (four different mean sizes), varied conditions have been applied (temperature fluctuation, PH, Contact Time, and Amount dosage as discussed before), and results have been concluded by batch experimentation and adsorption experimentation based on my study that is Levofloxacin adsorption using the corn husk and its activated carbon. My research work is novel in terms of the use of an expensive and easily available source of Corn husk biomass for the optimization of Levofloxacin can be productive shortly for covering the scientific gaps in earlier studies of Pakistan, also the agricultural waste will be utilized for an upright purpose and the wastewater can be treated efficiently with less environmental and health impact.

CONCLUSION

In this study, corn husk was utilized as a carrier to create adsorbent solutions in two different forms: with activated carbon and without activated carbon. The adsorption technique is observed as one of the most relevant technologies due to its safety, economy, and ease. This technique is extremely accurate to meet the low-cost goals, corn husks, and biomass (agricultural waste), were chosen as the primary source of adsorbent. It might not only minimize pharmaceutical contamination but also provide an extra option for the utilization of such type of agricultural waste. Furthermore, corn is a widespread and abundant crop, so it is inexpensive and easily available. Corn husks were converted into charcoal and the remainder into simple crushed form to boost adsorption capacity and recovery. The biochar solution has a higher absorbance capacity due to its small and fine powdered structure, and we have determined that the higher the solution's acidity, the higher its absorbance capacity is. Corn husks are inexpensive, and they are environmentally safe. Furthermore, they have great efficacy in removing pharmaceuticals from aqueous solutions. They may also be recycled and reused while still maintaining excellent adsorption capabilities. The SEM analysis shows that the absorbent can act as an absorbent; the nanocrystalline surface of bio adsorbent shows the pores and is also layered.

Nanoparticles indicated that antibiotics have been adsorbed on the structure of bio-sorbent and have taken the place of pores. The greater the mesh size of the crushed powder the higher it has absorbance efficiency, out of four sieve size parameters i.e., 200mm, 50mm, 30mm, and 10mm, the solution of 200 mm (both Activated carbon, simple solutions) has the efficient absorbance capacity. The smaller particle size has a larger surface area, which indicates that a given volume of solution is made up of smaller particles, so in turn, the substance's surface area rises (Zhang *et al.*, 2008). As a result, nanoparticle-based materials have a considerably higher surface area per unit volume ratio than bigger particle-based materials. Surface areas of nanoscale materials are much greater than those of equivalent masses of bigger-scale materials (RavishankarRai *et al.*, 2011). As a substance's surface area per mass rises due to this more of the material might come into touch with surrounding components, altering reactivity. Not just the smaller size (larger surface area) but also varied PH, temperature, contact time, amount dosage of the solution influenced the adsorption of the solution.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Pakistan and every country should opt for the adsorption technique for wastewater treatment techniques and utilize the biomass/ agricultural waste for an upright purpose, the corn husk enhances the effectiveness of antibiotic removal from the wastewater, and due to this the water has been treated, and can be reused repeatedly, so the less resource has been consumed and agricultural waste has also been utilized for the upright purposes.
2. This process is also an eco-friendly approach, no harmful chemicals have been used in the processing also no such emissions have been involved in the environment during treatment also it is cost-effective and easily available.
3. Organizations and management should abandon other conventional ways in favor of such approaches; the country's waste has been used for another waste treatment, saving many resources and investments; and the economy may benefit as a result.

Competing Interests: Authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding: Complete funding was provided by Government College University Lahore to complete the research work.

Authors' contributions: Muhammad Afzaal provided the main idea of the research work. Syeda Saira Iqbal assisted in manuscript formation, editing, and referencing. Rohama Nassir contributed to the literature review, results, and discussion. Neha Javid Johnworked on the introduction write-up and designing methodology. Aysha Arif worked on the methodology write-up and reviewed the whole article.

Acknowledgments: Acknowledgment goes to Government College University Lahore for providing space and facilities to complete the research work.

REFERENCES

- Abdi, O., M. Kazemi. 2015. A review study of biosorption of heavy metals and comparison between different biosorbents. *J Mater Environ Sci.* 6(5): 1386-1399.
- Ahmed, M. B., Zhou, J.L., Ngo, H.H., Guo, W. 2015. Adsorptive removal of antibiotics from water and wastewater: progress and challenges. *Science of the Total Environment.* 532: 112-126.

- Baig, U., Uddin, M. K., Gondal, M. A. 2020. Removal of hazardous azo dye from water using synthetic nano adsorbent: Facile synthesis, characterization, adsorption, regeneration, and design of experiments. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*. 584:124031.
- Balarak, D., Khatibi, A.D., Chandrika, K. 2020. Antibiotics removal from aqueous Solution and pharmaceutical wastewater by adsorption process: A review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Investigation*. 10(2):106-111.
- Bansal, R. C., Goyal, M. 2005. Activated carbon adsorption. CRC press.
- Brodin, T., Piovano, S., Fick, J., Klaminder, J., Heynen, M., Jonsson, M. 2014. Ecological effects of pharmaceuticals in aquatic systems—impacts through behavioral alterations. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*.369(1656): 20130580.
- Chen, Y., Shi, J., Du, Q., Zhang, H., Cui, Y. 2019. Antibiotic removal by agricultural waste biochar with different forms of iron oxide. *RSC advances*. 9(25):14143-14153.
- De Silveira, G., Forsberg, P., Conners, T. E. 2020. Scanning electron microscopy: A tool for the analysis of wood pulp fibers and paper. In *the Surface analysis of paper*. (41-71). CRC Press.
- Enders, A., Lehmann, J. 2012. Comparison of wet-digestion and dry-ashing methods for total elemental analysis of biochar. *Communications in soil science and plant analysis*. 43(7):1042-1052.
- Freitas, J. T., de Melo, C. C., Viana, O. M., Ferreira, F. F., Doriguetto, A. C. 2018. The crystal structure of levofloxacin hydrates is a high-temperature powder X-ray diffraction study versus crystal structure prediction. *Crystal Growth & Design*. 18(6):3558-3568.
- He, F., Cai, W., Lin, J., Yu, B., Owens, G., Chen, Z. 2021. Reducing the impact of antibiotics in wastewaters: Increased removal of mitoxantrone from wastewater by biosynthesized manganese nanoparticles. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 293:126207.
- Higuchi, H., Okamoto, E., Seki, K., Takada, H., Tamura, Y. 2020. Manure Compost Is a Potential Source of Tetracycline-Resistant *Escherichia coli* and Tetracycline Resistance Genes in Japanese Farms. *Antibiotics*. 9:76.
- Kraemer, S. A., Ramachandran, A., Perron, G. G. 2019. Antibiotic pollution in the environment: from microbial ecology to public policy. *Microorganisms*. 7(6):180.
- Li, N., Sheng, G. P., Lu, Y. Z., Zeng, R. J., Yu, H. Q. 2017. Removal of antibiotic resistance genes from wastewater treatment plant effluent by coagulation. *Water Research*. 111:204-212.
- Patel, N., Khan, M. D., Shahane, S., Rai, D., Chauhan, D., Kant, C., Chaudhary, V. K. 2020. Emerging pollutants in the aquatic environment: Source, effect, and challenges in biomonitoring and bioremediation-A review. *Pollution*. 6(1):99-113.
- Pinto, J., Cruz, D., Paiva, A., Pereira, S., Tavares, P., Fernandes, L., Varum, H. 2012. Characterization of corn cob as a possible raw building material. *Construction and Building Materials*, 34:P28-33.
- Pinto, J., Cruz, D., Paiva, A., Pereira, S., Tavares, P., Fernandes, L., Varum, H. 2012. Characterization of corn cob as a possible raw building material. *Construction and Building Materials*. 34:28-33.
- Rasschaert, G., Elst, D.V., Colson, L., Herman, L., Ferreira, H.C.C., Dewulf, J., Decrop, J., Meirlaen, J., Heyndrickx, M., Daeseleire, A.E. 2020. Antibiotic Residues and Antibiotic-Resistant Bacteria in Pig Slurry used to Fertilize Agricultural Fields. *Antibiotics*. 9:34.
- RavishankarRai, V. 2011. Nanoparticles and their potential application as antimicrobials.
- Sonune, A., Ghate, R. 2004. Developments in wastewater treatment methods. *Desalination*. 167: 55-63.

- Tan, X., Zhang, D., Duan, Z., Parajuli, K., Hu, J. 2020. Effects of light color on interspecific competition between microcystisaeruginosa and chlorella pyrenoidosa in a batch experiment. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 27(1): 344-352.
- Taylor, J. L., Holland, D. J., Keating, S. E., Leveritt, M. D., Gomersall, S. R., Rowlands, A. V., Coombes, J. S. 2020. Short-term and long-term feasibility, safety, and efficacy of high-intensity interval training in cardiac rehabilitation: the FITR heart study randomized clinical trial. *JAMA cardiology*. 5(12):1382-1389.
- Torres, E. 2020. Biosorption: A review of the latest advances. *Processes*. 8(12):1584.
- Wang, G., Wang, D., Xu, Y., Li, Z., Huang, L. 2020. Study on optimization and performance of biologically enhanced activated sludge process for pharmaceutical wastewater treatment. *Science of The Total Environment*. 739:140166.
- Yoshizawa, N., Usui, M., Fukuda, A., Asai, T., Higuch, H., Okamoto, E., Seki, K., Takada, H., Tamura, Y. 2020. Manure Compost Is a Potential Source of Tetracycline-Resistant *Escherichia coli* and Tetracycline Resistance Genes in Japanese Farms. *Antibiotics*. 9(2):76. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics9020076>
- Zhang, L., Gu, F.X., Chan, J.M., Wang, A.Z., Langer, R.S., Farokhzad, O.C. 2008. Nanoparticles in medicine: therapeutic applications and developments. *Clinical pharmacology & therapeutics*. 83(5):761-769.